

Supplementary information for manuscript

Nickel-cobalt spinel-based oxygen evolution electrode for zinc-air flow battery

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Figure S1: Schematics of ZAFB and the connection of sensing to the potentiostat including the lab made electronic for the switching between charging and discharge mode (OER and ORR electrode, respectively).

Figure S2: XRD spectrum of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode, confirming that prepared catalyst layer contains NiCo₂O₄ phase.

Figure S3: Images from scanning electron microscope for: a) pristine nickel mesh; b) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer.

Figure S4: Distribution of selected elements on surface of Ni mesh/NiCo₂O₄ electrode determined by SEM-EDS mapping of surface. a) SEM image of NiCo₂O₄/Ni electrode; b) distribution of Ni; c) distribution of Co; d) distribution of O.

Figure S5: Images from scanning electron microscope for: a) pristine nickel foam; b) detail of NiCo₂O₄ catalytic layer.

Figure S6: Distribution of selected elements on surface of nickel foam electrode determined by SEM-EDS mapping of surface. a) SEM image of $\text{NiCo}_2\text{O}_4/\text{Ni}$ electrode; b) distribution of Ni; c) distribution of Co; d) distribution of O.

1. Detailed discussion on electrolyte composition

Initial pH of fresh working electrolyte was 15.43, for pristine nickel mesh, it decreased to the value of 14.35 after the entire experiment (160 hours). The change of electrolyte pH during the experiment for all four electrodes are summarized in the last column of **Table S1**. The pH of counter electrolyte also changed (increased), but its deviation from original value was lower (for pristine nickel mesh pH increased to 16.165 during the experiment). Growth of $\eta_{\text{theo.}}$ between 2nd and 5th series was significant (see second column of **Table S1**). However, we can see that the corresponding change of $\eta_{\text{act.}}$ remained almost constant, as the actual OCP of working electrolyte also increased due to pH decrease. The evolution of OCP during the experiment is not linear within 5 series as the driving forces of electrolyte flux through the membrane changed in time. The OCP increase is the most significant within the 1st series, where the driving forces was the highest, from 2nd series the growth of the OCP in time is linear. The most pronounced OCP increase within the 1st series can be also at least partially related to the gradual saturation of electrolyte by evolving oxygen. From the Nernst equation for OER the change of pH by 1 is proportional to the change of the electrode OCP by 59.2 mV [1]. Little deviation of measured values from calculated ΔOCP values for each electrode was most probably caused by the effect of the oxygen dissolved in the working electrolyte, affecting the measured OCP values. Nevertheless, the observed increased $\eta_{\text{theo.}}$ are mostly affected by gradual change in electrolyte composition.

Table S1: Comparison of parameters change between at different stages of experiment evaluated from load curve measurements shown in **Figure S7**. **The Table S1 is the same as the Table 4 in manuscript.**

OER electrode	$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo.}} - \text{s.2-5} /$ mV at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta \eta_{\text{act.}} /$ mV at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta \eta_{\text{theo.}} \text{ s.2-6} /$ mV at 50 mA cm ⁻²	$\Delta \text{OCP} /$ mV	$\Delta \text{pH} / -$
Details of comparison	between series 2 and 5	between series 2 and 5	between series 2 and 6	between series 2 and 5	between series 1 and 5
Pristine mesh	82	24	14	58	-1.08
Catalysed mesh	75	23	21	44	-1.00
Pristine foam	69	36	3	62	-1.10
Catalysed foam	59	10	18	50	-1.06

Figure S7: a) Evolution of OER electrode potential within the mid-term stability experiment for the four Ni-based electrodes: pristine mesh (PM, yellow), catalysed mesh (CM, purple), pristine foam (PF, black) and catalysed foam (CF, blue). **Experimental conditions:** Electrolyte 8 mol dm^{-3} KOH, electrolyte flow rate 160 ml min^{-1} , $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, constant load for 6 hours at 50 mA cm^{-2} , load curve measurements ($0\text{--}100 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$, $1.25 \text{ mA cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), 5 series (each consists of 5 repetitions) and 2 more repetition after electrolyte change. **The figure S7 is the same as the Figure 5 in manuscript.**

1. Hausmann, J.N., et al., *The pH of Aqueous NaOH/KOH Solutions: A Critical and Non-trivial Parameter for Electrocatalysis*. ACS Energy Letters, 2021. **6**(10): p. 3567-3571.